

×*Puybergia* (*Billbergia* × *Puya*), a Replacement Name for ×*Billya* Bethmann ex M.H.J.van der Meer, nom. illeg. (Bromeliaceae)

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Abstract—The replacement name ×*Puybergia* for ×*Billya* Bethmann ex M.H.J.van der Meer non Cass. is proposed.

The nothogeneric name ×*Billya* Bethmann ex M.H.J.van der Meer (Bromeliaceae) ([Cact. Phantast. 2019\(7\)-2: 2. 2019](#)) is an illegitimate later homonym of *Billya* Cass. (Asteraceae). A replacement name is proposed here:

×*Puybergia* M.H.J.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Billbergia* Thunb. × *Puya* Molina. Based on ×*Puybergia* ‘Alpha’ Bethmann = *Billbergia* ‘Hallelujah’ D.A.Beadle × *Puya mirabilis* (Mez) L.B.Sm. ([Bromeliad Cultivar Register 12406](#), accessed March 2, 2022).

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